

REAL AREA OF CONTACT IN CARBON FABRIC FORMING

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ABSTRACT

An experimental rig and image analysis method have been developed to measure the real area of contact between carbon fibre fabric and a smooth tool. By using as the tool surface a flat glass slide with an optical coating, and viewing the contact through the slide, the contact area is clearly visible at a fibre scale. Straightforward image analysis is used to estimate the length of fibre contact. A microcontact density is defined, normalising the measured fibre contact length by the value for an idealised packing arrangement of close-packed parallel fibres. The method is applied to a 2×2 twill weave carbon fabric and a 12k carbon fibre single tow. Both for the woven fabric and the single tow, the microcontact density is significantly below the idealised value of 100%. The contact density is sensitive to contact pressure and has a similar value of between 4 and 8 % for the two materials considered at the contact pressure of a few kPa appropriate to dry pre-forming operations.

1 INTRODUCTION

There are a wide range of forming processes used for composites depending on the fibre architecture, shape complexity and cost. Increasing automation, particularly in the automobile industry, is driving development of a route using pre-forming of a range of dry fabrics and subsequent resin infusion. Alternatively pre-preg material can be formed using single or matched dies or by using diaphragm forming process. Considerable attention has been paid to the details of the material behaviour, including its draping characteristics. Rather less is known about friction between the composite fabric and the tools in these processes. Macroscopic experiments have determined friction coefficients for typical conditions [1-3]. However, without a clear idea of the mechanisms of friction, it can be difficult to apply such measurements with confidence away from the specific test conditions. It has been hypothesised that the fibres align in a regular manner at the contact [3-5] but this has not been verified.

Tribological assessments typically start with examining the contact conditions at a microscopic scale between surfaces [6]. Hence this paper describes a rig developed to examine the local fibre contact at a microscopic scale between carbon fibre material and a flat transparent glass 'tool'. Because shear of the fabric is a key mechanism of deformation in draping, the rig has been designed to accommodate such behaviour. The aim is that this microscopic examination of the contact can help gain understanding of the contact details, so as to inform both development of mathematical models and design of appropriate experiments that capture the essential mechanics of the contact. Moreover results can indicate the key variables which might be expected to influence frictional conditions in real forming processes.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

A key part of the experiment is development of a suitable surface to observe contact of the fibres. The idea of using a transparent surface is well established in the tribological community, both for static and dynamic tests, as this allows observation and measurement of the development of the contact and

the effect of lubricants. In the case of composites it is supposed that resin can provide some hydrodynamic support [7] and observation of the contact has allowed assessment of such effects in traditional lubrication experiments. Quantitative measurement of the gap uses optical interference techniques by means of coating layers, for example a semi-reflective chromium layer [8]. To measure ultra-thin lubrication gaps an additional SiO_2 spacer layer can be deposited on top of the Cr layer [9]. The thickness of the layers must be optimised to provide equal reflectance and transmittance so as to produce clear interference fringes. In the case of carbon fibres, a two layer coating, comprising an 8 nm chromium coating and a 140 nm thick silica coating (Tofico, France) was chosen to optimise the performance.

The second aspect of the rig was development of a suitable loading arrangement. Two variants were used. In the first variant, illustrated in Fig. 1, fabric was sheared along its bias direction using stepper motor actuators. The fabric was clamped in an ‘open shear’ arrangement, with the fabric being held on the four sides by rigid rods which forced a deformation mode intermediate between the more conventional bias extension and picture frame tests. This arrangement was required so that the material in the middle of the sample could be loaded normal to the plane of the fabric by glass plates on the top and bottom faces of the sample. The clamping force N was applied by a spring-loading arrangement, with the relationship between compression distance and force calibrated using a Flexiforce strip load cell. This loading method was applied to woven fabric, where shear of the material is seen as a critical mechanism of deformation which may influence the contact details. Further details of this arrangement are given in [11]. In the second loading variant, only normal force is applied to single tows, again through the glass plates. In this case button load cells are used to measure the normal contact force N .

The materials used for this study were both dry carbon fibre. For the fabric study a 2×2 twill woven T700 (C24k) carbon fibre fabric of areal weight 400gsm and without binder was used. For the tow study a Toray T700 12k 60E tow was used.

Figure 1: Illustration of open-frame loading rig showing motor drives elongating a fabric sample clamped between two glass plates. The normal load N is applied via a screw-spring arrangement and the elongation load F is measured with load cells.

3 IMAGE ANALYSIS

By using glass plates to apply a normal load to the sample, it is possible to view the contact patch using a microscope, see Fig. 2. For the fabric study the magnification and camera setup used corresponded to a pixel side length of $1.515 \mu\text{m}$, while the tow study used a higher resolution with a pixel side length of $0.578 \mu\text{m}$. The areas used in the analysis were $19.3 \times 16.3 \text{ mm}$ for the woven material and $9.5 \times 4.4 \text{ mm}$ for the single tow case. Figure 2(a) shows a typical observation from the fabric study. The bright contact areas are clearly visible with the optical coating used. To identify these automatically, a combination of thresholding and filtering was used. The thresholding was used to find the bright pixels, while filtering was used to identify those bright pixels corresponding to the long thin fibre features being sought. The result of this image analysis is seen in Fig. 2(b), where the fibre contacts are highlighted in red. While the imaging method is able to quantify the length of contact, the resolution is insufficient to measure accurately the width of the contact patches. Instead it is suggested that a Hertz modelling approach is used to estimate the width, see [11]. Further details of the algorithms used are given in [10].

Figure 2: (a) Microscope image of a typical area of the fabric sample,
(b) fibre contact regions highlighted in red.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Twill weave fabric

Figure 3 illustrates the pattern of fibre contact observed for the woven fabric at a compressive load of 1.77 N, corresponding to a nominal contact pressure of 1.9 kPa. The intermittent nature of the contact at the mesoscale of the tows is clearly visible. The central dark region corresponds to a mesoscale contact patch where a tow lying on the top of the fabric makes contact with the glass plate. However it is also clear that there is considerable disorganisation in the fibres. The contact geometry is far from the idealised picture of closely-packed parallel fibres touching each other, but instead there is a range of fibre orientations. This leads to a significantly reduced contact area.

To quantify the contact arrangement, a tow microcontact density $D_{mic/tow}$ is defined by taking the ratio of the length of contact L measured within an area A and the contact length A/d that would be present for parallel closely packed fibres of diameter d , expressing this as a percentage to give:

$$D_{mic/tow} = \frac{dL}{A} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Considering the area within the macro-contact of the tows, the variation of this microcontact density with the angle of shear of the fabric is plotted in Fig. 4. The amount of shear was estimated from the observed fibre orientations. A microcontact density D of 100% corresponds to an ideal packing geometry. Figure 4 shows that the microcontact density is much less than this ideal value, taking values of around 2-3% for the lower load of 0.23 N (corresponding to a normal pressure of 0.26 kPa) and between 4 and 8 % at the higher load of 1.77 N (pressure of 1.9 kPa). The microcontact density does not vary significantly with shear angle at the lower load, but does fall somewhat with increasing shear for the two tests for the higher load cases. It was hypothesised that shear might increase the ability of fibres to slide other one another and so increase the contact density, but this is not supported by the evidence.

Figure 3: Contact area for woven fabric at a contact pressure of 1.9 kPa.

Figure 4: Effect of shear angle on the tow microcontact density, averaged over the area within four tow mesoscale contact patches. A microcontact density of 100% corresponds to an idealised arrangement of parallel close-packed fibres.

4.2 Unidirectional tow

Figure 5 illustrates the contact patch for the unidirectional tow at the start and end of a test with progressively increased load, corresponding to nominal contact pressures of 0.6 and 270 kPa, respectively.

The variation of tow microcontact density with nominal pressure is given in Fig. 6. At the beginning of the test (i.e. Fig. 5(a), which shows a subsection of the entire scan), filament contact is sparse with only 3% microcontact density. Tow microcontact density then exhibits a non-linear increase with pressure that could be described by an empirical power-law of the type $D = \alpha p^\beta$ (where p is the normal pressure and α and β are empirical constants). At a pressure of 5 kPa (comparable to the maximum pressure in the fabric tests of 1.9 kPa) the microcontact density is around 7 %, similar to the value seen for the fabric of 4-8 %.

At the maximum pressure of 270 kPa the microcontact density is just over 30%, with the nominal contact patch having areas of dense filament contact connected by less dense regions (see Fig. 5b). As pressure is increased even further, the microcontact density is expected to approach a limiting value considerably below the ideal value of 100%. Figure 6 suggests that, for the present experiment, this value is probably less than 50%, but this requires further investigation. Since in these experiments the tow can achieve a nominally flat topography, this limiting value is seen as an upper bound for contact in processes such as woven fabric forming, where the contact density will be lower owing to the non-flat surface.

Figure 5. Fibre contact detection at the start and end of a test on a single tow, showing a 1.18×0.89 mm part of the entire 9.5×4.4 mm scan: (a) tow nominal pressure 0.6 kPa, and (b) tow nominal pressure 270 kPa.

Figure 6. Effect of contact pressure on microcontact density in a single tow.

5 CONCLUDING DISCUSSION

Microscopic observations of the contact geometry between carbon fibre material and a glass optically-coated surface have revealed the details of the contact at the meso and microscopic scale. Both a 2×2 twill weave and a single tow have been considered. The contact geometry is far from an idealised arrangement of parallel close-packed fibres, with random orientations of the fibres limiting the contact length. The effect of fabric shear on the microscopic contact geometry appears relatively modest.

The sensitivity of the microcontact density to pressure illustrates the importance of understanding the fundamental tribology of the contact in order to inform experiments and models. Work is in hand to extend the range of materials considered and to include resin lubrication. The observed variation in microcontact density with pressure will be important in terms of understanding tow friction, since friction depends on the real contact area (i.e. $F = \tau A$). The maximum contact pressure in the single tow tests of 270 kPa is significantly higher than the maximum value of 1.9 kPa used in the fabric tests. The value of a few kPa for fabric tests was chosen as typical of conditions in dry pre-forming or draping operations, where friction modelling will be needed to understand generation of wrinkles or other defects. Pressures of the order of hundreds of kPa might correspond to the final stages of a matched tool process where slip of the fabric is less likely to result in generation of defects in the part.

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